

1	..	3	..	5	..	14	..	22	..	34	..	36	..	50	51	52	..	60	..	119
---	----	---	----	---	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	-----

Available features. Randomly selected for the initial population or by the crossover and mutation operators

5	14	22	34	36	50	51	52	60
---	----	----	----	----	----	----	----	----

Chromosome

Accessing to the database to build an individual

	Features																			
	1	..	5	..	14	..	22	..	34	..	36	..	50	51	..	60	..	119		
1																				
2																				
...																				
N																				

Database

Individual

.....

	Features								
	5	14	22	34	50	51	52	60	
1									
2									
....									
N									

Individual

